

AI and Academic Integrity Survey Instrument

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This survey instrument was used in the study “AI and Academic Integrity: Exploring Student Perceptions and Implications for Higher Education” (Lund et al., 2025). Researchers are welcome to use this tool or individual questions with proper attribution. Questions were developed through literature review and refined via pilot testing.

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
<i>Cheating on assignments hurts others besides me</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
<i>Cheating is acceptable if I don't get caught</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
<i>Using AI to help write papers is a form of cheating</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>					
<i>Using AI on assignments is not an ethical issue</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>					

Demographic Information

6. Educational Status:

- *Undergraduate Student*
- *Master's/Professional Program Student*
- *Doctoral Student*

7. Major (e.g., "data science," "history"):

8. Student Type:

- *International Student*
- *Domestic (U.S.-based) Student*

9. Gender Identity:

- *Male*
- *Female*
- *Non-binary / Non-conforming*
- *Identity not listed (please specify): _____*
- *Prefer not to say*

10. Primary Language:

(Spoken most often at home/outside professional settings)

References

Lund, B. D., Lee, T. H., Mannuru, N. R., & Arutla, N. (2025). AI and academic integrity: Exploring student perceptions and implications for higher education. *Journal of Academic Ethics*.

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